

CHALLENGES IN THE PROJECT MANAGEMENT PRACTICES OF REMOTE TEAMS

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Abstract

Purpose – Given how the number of remote teams has increased, and how these types of teams face a set of particular issues on top of the common issues that regular teams face, a need for a set of tools and techniques to help address these issues emerge. That constitutes the central point of the paper.

Methodology/approach – The research was conducted by examining the particularities of remote and software remote teams, their project management practices and the particularities of remote agile implications. Based on this, a set of tools and techniques that remote teams can use has been proposed.

Findings – The research indicates that there are a set of project management practices from agile methodologies and lessons learned from software remote teams that could benefit remote teams.

Research limitations/implications – Lack of research in the field of remote teams from various fields.

Practical implications – The inability to reach out and test the proposed set of tools and techniques on various remote teams working in different fields.

Originality/value – Proposing a set of tools and techniques that remote teams can use in order to address the most pressing issues that they face.

Key words: project management, remote, agile

Introduction

In today's socio-economic context where most of the businesses aim for globalization and are encouraged to do so, and furthermore, where the needs of various companies are met with the help of remote teams, the requirement for an adequate project management approach emerges. The number of companies turning to remote or virtual teams has increased significantly in recent years (Ásólfsdóttir, 2012) (Ford, Piccolo, & Ford, 2016), with research showing that approximately 66 percent of multinational organizations use virtual teams (Gilson, et al. 2015).

An important aspect to consider regarding the popularity of remote teams is that it has been noted that although these were predominantly used in fields such as software development, we can now witness companies from various occupational fields such as: accounting, applied psychology, business management, communication, education, and engineering (Gilson, et al. 2015) taking advantage of the benefits that remote teams bring. Furthermore, world events such as the COVID-19 pandemic has pushed even more teams to become remote (Zimmermann 2020), thus reiterating the necessity of understanding how remote teams work and what can be done to increase their productivity and the overall wellbeing of remote workers.

A large number of definitions exist to describe the terms remote team and virtual team (Ásólfsdóttir 2012) (Ford, Piccolo and Ford 2016) (Ravi, Drake and Liang 2016) (Gilson, et al. 2015), their common point being that remote teams are made of individuals working together towards a common goal, even if they are not clustered together in the same building, or often cities, and even countries.

This dispersion can in turn impact the way the work is organized and targets are met. Research has focused on identifying the key factors that influence the efficiency and the way in which remote teams

work together and has found that among others, the most prominent factors are: management ability, culture (especially significant amongst teams distributed across multiple countries), the time zones, the team cohesion, the set of project management tools used and the quality management practices (Ásólfisdóttir 2012).

Even so, the benefits of remote teams outweigh the issues that arise. These benefits include: reduce costs for sourcing talent regardless of geography, increased diversity and flexibility, maintain a workflow across different time zone (Choi, 2018), reduced time to market and the possibility of following critical-path tasks around the clock (Vallon, Estácioc, Prikladnicki, & Grechenig, 2018).

Lately, a trend in the way that remote software development teams are organizing their workflow has been observed and it relates to the implementation of agile principles and practices (Shrivastava and Date 2010) (Collins, et al. 2012) (Sharp, et al. 2016) (Sepulveda 2003) (Keeling, Clements-Croome and Roesch 2015) (Phalnikar, Deshpande and Joshi 2009) (Vallon, et al. 2018) in order to increase productivity and alleviate some of the issues that arise from working remotely. At the same time, the trend of implementing agile practices has been noted in other occupational fields as well (Serrador and Pinto 2015) (Paasivaara, Durasiewicz and Lassenius 2009).

In this paper, we analyze the difficulties encountered by remote teams along with the possibility of using some of the techniques used by software remote teams and principles of agile development for addressing some of these issues.

Research problem

Remote teams are becoming an essential aspect of the way that work is conducted worldwide, and this trend has shown a significant increase in the past couple of months due to the situation created as a consequence of the COVID-19 pandemic. These remote teams have proven to be a viable alternative when there's an impossibility of teams working together in the same space, this alternative being already more thoroughly explored by teams working in the software industry.

Although remote teams can be highly effective and bring about a set of particular benefits that regular teams do not, research shows that they are also prone to encountering more issues than regular teams and requiring more management involvement in order to be efficient.

Furthermore, an interesting trend emerged among remote teams and that is the implementation of agile methodologies and principles for their project management. Agile practices emphasize the importance of fast prototyping and delivery, adaptability to changes in customer requirements and self-organizing teams.

Given how remote teams are becoming a necessity and how these teams face a set of particular issues along with the common issues that regular teams face, manifests the need for a set of tools and techniques to help address these issues.

In our research, we have focused on addressing the following research questions:

RQ1: Are there differences in the way that remote teams and regular teams organize their work?

RQ2: Are there differences in the way these types of teams address the issues that arise before or during the development process?

RQ3: Are there differences when using a traditional project management approach and an agile development approach in the case of remote teams?

Methodology

The research was conducted by first examining the particularities of remote teams, and observing their plusses and minuses, along with their project management practices. The literature was consulted in regard to this matter. Similarly, the literature was consulted in order to observe and draw conclusions

on software remote teams project management practices and agile methodologies, and their proven effectiveness. From here, based on the results obtained after analyzing the data, a set of tools and techniques that remote teams can use in order to address the most pressing issues that they face was proposed.

The research articles that were reviewed in the paper were selected from Google Scholar and Researchgate by searching for key terms such as: “remote teams”, “remote agile”, “agile teams”, “distributed teams”, “virtual teams”, “globalized teams”, in the 2012 – 2020 interval. After this initial step, the most relevant articles have been selected by reading the abstract and conclusions. The next step involved the in-depth reading of the articles and their findings in order to help answer the research questions.

A second round of searching and reviewing relevant research articles took place, based on the bibliography and suggestions from the previously reviewed scientific articles. Similarly, articles were first checked for relevancy by reading the abstract and conclusions, then were read and their findings were analyzed.

Based on the findings, suggestions and observations of the reviewed scientific articles, the conclusions were formed in order to answer the research questions. Furthermore, suggestions were formed in order to help propose a set of tools and techniques that can be used by remote teams to address some of the issues that they face.

Findings

The first significant aspect discovered through the analysis of scientific articles in the field was related to the definition of remote teams, and understanding the various forms that they can take. Figure 1 shows the three main types of remote teams that have been identified in literature (Sharp, et al. 2016) and their particularities.

Remote teams		
Distributed <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Overall team is split between locations but everyone in the sub-team is co-located with others in the sub-team 	Dispersed <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Each team member is located in a different place, and is on their own 	Hybrid <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A small number of team members are located elsewhere separately, but there is a co-located team

Fig. 1. Types of remote teams

Based on these descriptions of types of remote teams, the authors identified that for the articles reviewed in the current paper, the majority of the case studies examined remote work in hybrid teams. Knowing the various types of remote teams and their particularities is helpful in understanding how teams work in these different scenarios and which tools are best fit for each case.

The identified challenges that arise from managing and working with and within a remote team are presented in Figure 2 and they relate not only to the technical issues that team encounter but also take into account the social aspects. The types of issues that remote teams deal with can be grouped into four main categories as follows: issues raised by the tools used, knowledge management issues, project management issues and communication issues. It can be observed that the project management and communication categories are the ones with most entries, showing that these are an essential aspect

of ensuring effectiveness of remote teams. If, in the case of ordinary teams, communication tools do not pose that much importance, as most of the communication takes place in face-to-face setups that are easily accessible at any time during the workday, in the case of remote teams, proper communication is vital as these teams might even be working in different time zones and could go on for weeks at times without speaking to one another. Besides these, it has been noted that trust is even harder to build among remote teams (Ford, Piccolo and Ford 2016), and that less importance is given to team building activities in these teams (Sharp, et al. 2016), even though communication and trust is one of the major issues in remote teams (Du, et al. 2018).

Fig. 2. Issues encountered by remote teams

Regarding the importance of communication and team cohesion, it has been shown that collaboration has a significant impact on building team trust and the overall effectiveness of the team, and that knowledge sharing is one of the factors that has a positive influence on collaboration (Alsharo, Gregg și Ramirez 2017). In order to address the communication issues that remote teams face, most research focused on identifying the tools that can mediate the communication process of remote teams, from using dedicated software tools (Ravi, Drake and Liang 2016) (Giuffrida and Dittrich 2015) (Paasivaara, Durasiewicz and Lassenius 2009) (Costa, Lemos and Beck 2018) to developing VR headsets (Du, et al. 2018). At the same time, authors have noted that for remote teams, building trust can be somewhat easily achieved, and even more important issue regarding the enduring quality of trust emerges. This in turn has been linked to an effective coordination (Ravi, Drake and Liang 2016).

Agile methodologies have been implemented in the case of remote teams in order to increase project quality and performance, create trust between team members (Shrivastava and Date 2010), increase stakeholder satisfaction and manage projects (Serrador and Pinto 2015) but also due to their suitability for high uncertainty projects (Paasivaara, Durasiewicz and Lassenius 2009). Furthermore, it has been shown that the application of Agile in projects has a statistically significant impact on all three dimensions of project success (Serrador and Pinto 2015).

As a result of the implementation and usage of Agile methodologies in the case of remote teams, but also thanks to the added experience of remote teams from the software development field, a series of lessons learned and advice has been provided by the available literature. Therefore, in the case of remote teams, the most important aspect to be taken into account is clarity of objectives and making sure that everyone from the development team understands what is required of them and what the overall goal of the project is (Ásólfisdóttir 2012) (Ravi, Drake and Liang 2016) (Lindsjörn, et al. 2016), closely followed by team communication and collaboration and usage of appropriate management and communication tools.

Fig. 3. Issues encountered by remote teams

Figure 3 shows an overview of the recommendations formed by the research which was analyzed in the current paper. It can therefore be observed that the five major areas of importance when managing a remote team are: clarity of objectives, leadership, project management, communication and technology.

Answering *RQ1*, the research has shown that there are differences in the way that remote and regular teams organize their work, and these are mainly linked to the way objectives are established and team work is managed.

Furthermore, research revealed that there are differences in the way issues are dealt with by remote teams and regular teams (*RQ2*). The most significant differences are caused by communication channels and lack of policies and face-to-face interaction between team members of remote teams. More so, a lack of clear objectives and adequate project management tools leads to even more issues for remote teams.

Lastly, when addressing *RQ3: Are there differences when using a traditional project management approach and an agile development approach in the case of remote teams?* It has been noted that agile practices, particularly the Scrum methodology of the agile approach, can greatly benefit remote teams, with case studies showing an increase in efficiency and overall deliverables quality.

Discussion and conclusions

The aim of the paper was to analyze various research studies conducted in the field of remote teams and the problems that they encounter, with the purpose of proposing a set of tools and techniques that remote teams from various fields can use in order to address the most pressing issues that they face. The set is built from lessons learned by remote software teams and remote teams using agile methodologies.

The research indicates that there is a set of project management practices from agile methodologies that could benefit remote teams. Furthermore, a set of lessons learned from software teams can be applied to remote teams in order to improve their efficiency and ensure success. Figure 4 presents the main ideas drawn from lessons learned when dealing with remote teams and remote teams using one or more agile development methodologies.

Fig. 4 Recommendations for building and managing remote teams

Further research endeavors are based on the following two main directions:

1. testing the assumptions made with the help of an empirical study targeting preferably both software remote teams and remote teams from a different field of study.
2. examining the possibility of using specific quality management tools and practices in the project management of remote teams to help address some of the issues that they are faced with.

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